

Sub-Lethal Effects of Methoxyfenozide On Development and Fecundity of Tobacco Cutworm, *Spodoptera litura* (Fabricius) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) On Cauliflower

Malik A.Q.¹, Sahito H.A.^{2*}, Kousar T.², Mal B.³, Abbasi N.A.⁴, Soomro A.A.⁴, Jaffery S.M.⁴, Mastoi S.M.⁴, Jatoi F.A.², Mangrio W.M.²

¹Pak Fumigation Systems Suite #. 603, 6th Floor, Landmark Plaza, I.I., Chandigarh Road, Karachi, Sindh.

²Department of Entomology, Faculty of Crop Protection, SAU, Tandojam, Sindh.

³Department of Zoology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, SALU, Khairpur Mir's, Sindh.

⁴Southern Zone Agricultural Research Center, Pest Management Research Institute, PARC, Karachi, Sindh.

*Corresponding author: Dr. Sahito H.A., Ph., # (92) 301-3515723, E-mail: hakim.sahito@salu.edu.pk

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ABSTRACT:

The mortality and sub-lethal effects were determined on development of surviving of *S. litura* on Insect growth regulator, Methoxyfenozide 240 SC (Dose: 1680, 1440, 1200, 960 and 720 ppm, were dissolved in water and each treatment was replicated 3 times. The results indicated that the copulation time, fecundity and fertility decreased when compared with control (distilled water). The maximum mortality observed on dose one after one week and minimum on dose five after 24 hours with the maximum larval weight reduction on dose one and dose three after 24 hours. The longest larval and pupal period, short adult longevity, maximum pupal weight reduction, longest duration of life-cycle, shortest copulation time, minimum fecundity and minimum fertility of eggs were recorded in dose one and highest in dose five. It is concluded that the methoxyfenozide (IGR) effective by their sub-lethal concentrations however, most preference can be given to which caused highly sub-lethal effects on the reproduction and biology of *S. litura* under laboratory conditions.

Keyword: *Reproduction, S. litura, IGR, Impact, B. oleracea.*

INTRODUCTION

Cauliflower, *Brassica oleracea* (L.) belongs to family Brassicaceae which is cultivated in cool season; it was originated before 2,000 years ago [1, 2]. Pakistan occupies top ten positions in the production of cauliflower in the world, about 13.6 thousand of harvested area cultivated and 235.4 thousand tons produced [3]. It has many nutritional values as contains carbohydrates, proteins, magnesium, calcium, moisture, calories, potassium, sodium, oxalic acids, vitamin A and C, largely cultivated in foggy coastal climates due to grown well in cool climates [4] about, 24 insect pests attack to cauliflower [5]. Among major insect pests, *Spodoptera litura* (F.) is also one, which is found in many tropical and sub-tropical regions of many countries including Pakistan. It is polyphagous insect pest, attacks about more than 150 species [6].

Even though these species conveyed in India are *S. pectin* Guen., *S. abyssinia* Guen., *S. compta* Moore., *S. downsei* B. also, *S. mauritia acronyctoides* Guen., [7, 8]. The issue of this insect is additionally amplified because of its immediate assault on fruiting structures, ravenous encouraging propensities, high portability and fecundity, covering era, nighttime conduct, and inclination for getting resistance against insect sprays [9, 10, 11]. Diverse types of *Spodoptera* are discovered viz., *S. litura* (Fabricius), *S. exempta* (Walker), *S. exigua* (Hubner), *S. frugiperda* (Smith) and *S. littoralis* (Boisd), most species are transient as grown-ups inside Africa, Asia and America. Among every one of these species, *S. litura* is a polyphagous creepy crawly making broad harm to farming and green products [12, 13]. About, 27% pesticides are applied on vegetables and fruits in Pakistan, which do not only increase production but also beneficial to quick control of dangerous pests [14]. Major crops losses 10% and 30% yield due

to this pest. It is necessary that vegetables must spray repeatedly due to they are quickly attacked by many insect pests as well as they have short duration time, cauliflower should spray 15 to 17 times during its growing period [15]. Methoxyfenozide, an insect growth regulator (IGR), is the newest and most potent member of the molt-accelerating compounds (MACs) against Lepidoptera [16]. This compound mimics the natural insect molting hormone by binding competitively to ecdysteroid receptors in insect cells, thus inducing a premature larval molt [17]. It can be incorporated in the integrated pest management (IPM) due to its short persistence, low eco-toxicological effects [18] and safety against non-target organisms as compared to the conventional insecticides [19, 20]. Due to a high septicity of its action against Lepidoptera, it is considered as an environmentally friendly compound [21]. However, no work has been carried out on methoxyfenozide based products against insect pests of cauliflower in Province Sindh, Pakistan. In the present study laboratory based results have been tested in the fields and the efficacy of methoxyfenozide has been compared against tobacco cutworm pest of cauliflower under lab conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of *S. litura* and culture maintenance

The egg masses as well the different stages of larvae were collected from different cauliflower unsprayed fields located at tauka Tando allahyar and reared at Bio-control lab at Department of Entomology Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam during, 2015-2016 under laboratory conditions at constant temperature of 25±2°C and relative humidity 60-65%. The all strains were collected by walking randomly later on, the collected egg masses and larvae were reared on fresh cauliflower leaves for maintaining

culture in glass cages (2x4") kept at laboratory conditions. The food was provided on daily basis up to the larvae transformed in to pupae. When these pupae were confirmed on an alternate days, were placed in to separate petri dishes with the filter paper to avoid the dehydrations. After cocoons when these adopted an adult stages were placed in glass jars separately in couples for copulating and oviposition process along with the cotton swamp which was soaked with the honey solution and glucose mixture with water. When these adults were laid eggs on green leaves of cauliflower on the under surface of leaves, such oviposited leaves were separated and kept those batches individually in different ventilated plastic jars (5-7 kg) for hatching and experimental purpose. Then, the fourth instar of tobacco cutworms larvae were collected from culture to observe the sub lethal effect of this insect growth regulator. The experiment was initiated with 600 number of 4th instar larvae. These larvae were treated with Methoxyfenozide 240 SC at five variable doses. Experiments were comprised of (IGR) treatment with five concentration.

Experimental design

There were five concentrations (sub-lethal doses) of Insect growth regulator, Methoxyfenozide 240 SC (Dose; 1680, 1440, 1200, 960 and 720 ppm dissolved in one liter of water) with control (Distilled water). The single treatment concentration was replicated 3times for its proper confirmation of mortality purpose. Methoxyfenozide solution was prepared in the bucket and cauliflower leaves were dipped in each concentration for 10-15 seconds and kept to dry in corridor shade. Treated food was given to ten larvae of each concentration of 4th instar to feed. A larva was considered deceased if it futile to move in a synchronized manner, when probed with blunt needle or camel hair bursh. Observation was recorded on surviving insects after the treatment with sub lethal effects and recorded the mortality, duration of life cycle, larval growth, pupal weight, pupal period, sex ratio (σ : ω), copulation time, fecundity and fertility, respectively.

Statistical analysis

Finally, the data was inserted in MS, excel spread sheet and latter on imported for analysis of variance for examination the significant results with the help of SXW software, 8.1, version (USA).

RESULTS

The results of the methoxyfenozide on the biological parameters of *S. litura* on percentage of larval mortality after 24 hours were varied significantly ($F= 18.50$; $DF=4, 74$; $P=0.002$) on different doses. At 1st dose, the highest mortality (16.67 $\pm$ 3.33; at 1680 ppm) percentage was recorded followed by (13.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 1440 ppm), (3.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 1200 ppm), (3.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 960 ppm) and (0.00 $\pm$ 0.00 at 720 ppm). The mortality after 48 hours at dose two, the highest mortality percentage was recorded at (56.67 $\pm$ 3.33; at 1680 ppm) followed by (56.67 $\pm$ 3.33 at 1440 ppm), (23.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 960 ppm), (13.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 720 ppm) and (3.33 $\pm$ 6.67 at 1200 ppm). The highest mortality percentage was recorded after application at dose three (76.67 $\pm$ 3.33; at 1680 ppm) followed by (66.67 $\pm$ 6.67 at 1440 ppm), (50.00 $\pm$ 5.77 at 1200 ppm), (23.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 960 ppm) and (23.33 $\pm$ 3.33 at 720 ppm) after 72 hours. The mortality after 96 hours at dose four, the maximum mortality percentage was recorded after application (80.00 $\pm$ 0.00; at 1680 ppm) followed by (70.00 $\pm$ 5.77; at 1440 ppm), (53.33 $\pm$ 6.67; at 1200 ppm), (30.00 $\pm$ 5.77; at 960 ppm) and (23.33 $\pm$ 3.33; at 720 ppm). Thus, the highest mortality percentage was recorded after application at dose five (80.00 $\pm$ 0.00; at 1680 ppm) followed by (70.00 $\pm$ 5.77; at 1400 ppm), (53.33 $\pm$ 6.67; at 1200 ppm), (30.00 $\pm$ 5.77; at 960 ppm) and (23.33 $\pm$ 3.33; at 720 ppm) after one week (Table- 1).

The larval weight of *S. litura* varied non-significantly ($F= 22.05$; $DF=5, 107$; $P=0.002$) after application of insecticide. At dose one, the highest larval weight reduction percentage of *S. litura* was recorded (24.88 $\pm$ 0.08; at 1680 ppm) followed by (16.98 $\pm$ 0.09; at 1440 ppm), (8.60 $\pm$ 0.09; at 960 ppm), (8.22 $\pm$ 0.05; at 720 ppm) and (6.30 $\pm$ 0.15; at 1200 ppm). After 48 hours, at dose two, the highest larval weight reduction percentage was recorded (32.69 $\pm$ 0.04; at 1680 ppm) followed by (27.26 $\pm$ 0.04; at 1440 ppm), (19.26 $\pm$ 0.12; at 960 ppm), (17.21 $\pm$ 0.07; at 1200 ppm) and (14.61 $\pm$ 0.03; at 720 ppm). After 72 hours, the highest larval weight reduction percentage was recorded after application of dose three (62.05 $\pm$ 0.19; at 1440 ppm) followed by (59.83 $\pm$ 0.11; at 1680 ppm), (41.24 $\pm$ 0.13; at 1200 ppm), (36.29 $\pm$ 0.11; at 960 ppm) and (31.18 $\pm$ 0.06; at 720 ppm). After 96 hours, at dose four, the mortality percentage of *S. litura* the maximum larval weight reduction percentage was recorded after application of (80.16 $\pm$ 0.02; at 1680 ppm) followed by (77.29 $\pm$ 0.28; at 1440 ppm), (58.30 $\pm$ 0.08; at 1200 ppm), (44.78 $\pm$ 0.12; at 960 ppm) and (38.82 $\pm$ 0.11; at 720 ppm). After one week, the highest larval weight reduction percentage was recorded after application at dose five (83.01 $\pm$ 0.03; at 1680 ppm) followed by (81.76 $\pm$ 0.22; at 1440 ppm), (63.71 $\pm$ 0.06; at 1200 ppm), (52.31 $\pm$ 0.07; at 960 ppm) and (44.55 $\pm$ 0.12; at 720 ppm) (Table- 2).

The larval period of *S. litura* varied significantly ($F= 991.02$; $DF=4, 48$; $P=0.001$) after application of insecticides. The maximum larval period of *S. litura* was recorded in (27.17 $\pm$ 0.60; at 1680 ppm) followed by (25.83 $\pm$ 0.26; at 1440 ppm), (24.40 $\pm$ 0.12; at 1200 ppm), (23.63 $\pm$ 0.26; at 960 ppm), (22.33 $\pm$ 0.08; at 720 ppm) and control (14.23 $\pm$ 0.09; at 00 ppm). The pupal period of *S. litura* varied significantly ($F= 292.88$; $DF=4, 48$; $P=0.001$) after application of insecticide. The highest pupal period of *S. litura* was recorded in (12.06 $\pm$ 0.44; at 1680 ppm) followed by (11.50 $\pm$ 0.30; at 1440 ppm), (10.20 $\pm$ 0.55; at 1200 ppm), (9.16 $\pm$ 0.24; at 960 ppm), (8.20 $\pm$ 0.11; at 720 ppm) and control (6.80 $\pm$ 0.15; at 00 ppm). The pupal weight of *S. litura* varied non-significant ($F= 0.97$; $DF=4, 48$; $P=0.4334$) after application of insecticide. The pupal weight was highly reduced (42.23 $\pm$ 0.63; at 1680 ppm) followed by (40.33 $\pm$ 0.49; at 1440 ppm), (37.60 $\pm$ 0.75; at 1200 ppm), (35.80 $\pm$ 0.75; at 960 ppm), (33.53 $\pm$ 0.18; at 720 ppm) and control (24.03 $\pm$ 0.34; at 00 ppm). The developmental time of *S. litura* varied significantly ($F= 1352.06$; $DF=4, 48$; $P=0.000$) after application of insecticide. The maximum developmental time of *S. litura* was recorded in (42.23 $\pm$ 0.63; at 1680 ppm) followed by (40.33 $\pm$ 0.49; at 1440 ppm), (37.60 $\pm$ 0.75; at 1200 ppm), (35.80 $\pm$ 0.75; at 960 ppm), (33.53 $\pm$ 0.18; at 720 ppm) and control (24.03 $\pm$ 0.34; at 00 ppm). The adult longevity of *S. litura* varied significantly ($F= 84.69$; $DF=4, 48$; $P=0.001$) after application of insecticide. The minimum longevity of *S. litura* was recorded in (10.36 $\pm$ 0.38; at 720 ppm) followed by (9.83 $\pm$ 0.52; at 960 ppm), (8.63 $\pm$ 0.26; at 1200 ppm), (8.13 $\pm$ 0.03; at 1440 ppm), (7.06 $\pm$ 0.41; at 1680 ppm) and control (11.83 $\pm$ 0.44; at 00 ppm). The total life period of *S. litura* varied significantly ($F= 749.78$; $DF=4, 48$; $P=0.001$) after application of insecticide. The highest total life period of *S. litura* was recorded in (49.36 $\pm$ 0.29; at 1680 ppm) followed by (48.33 $\pm$ 0.34; at 1440 ppm), (46.23 $\pm$ 0.90; at 1200 ppm), (45.76 $\pm$ 0.76; at 960 ppm), (44.06 $\pm$ 0.31; at 720 ppm) and control (35.86 $\pm$ 0.73; at 00 ppm) (Table- 3). Therefore, the sex proportion demonstrates that the males of *S. litura* were more susceptible to this IGR treated at different doses when compared with the female ones. Mostly, the sex ratio under given results indicated that the (5:13 at 960 ppm) followed by (5:13 at 960 ppm), (3:5 at 1440 ppm), (1:4 at 1680 ppm), (1:3 at 1200 ppm), (1:2 at 720 ppm) and control (1:2 at 00 ppm) of (σ : ω), respectively (Table- 4).

The copulation time of *S. litura* varied non-significant ($F= 0.07$; $DF=4, 29$; $P=0.991$) after application of insecticide (Table- 5). The minimum copulation time of *S. litura* was recorded in (20.66±0.33; at 720 ppm) followed by (22.66±0.16; at 960 ppm), (25.16±0.33; at 1200 ppm), (27.83±0.16; at 1440 ppm), (30.16±0.33; at 1680 ppm) and control (57.00±00; at 00 ppm). The fecundity of females of *S. litura* varied non-significantly ($F= 0.02$; $DF=4, 29$; $P=0.998$) after application of insecticide. The lowest fecundity of females of *S. litura* was recorded in (341.67±7.54; at

1680 ppm) followed by (356.67±1.33; at 960 ppm), (365.33±4.67; at 1440 ppm), (402.00±3.51; at 1200 ppm), (483.00±4.04; at 720 ppm) and control (1178.00±50.52; at 00 ppm). The fertility percentage of females of *S. litura* varied non-significant ($F= 0.02$; $DF=4, 29$; $P=0.998$) after application of insecticide. The lowest fertility percentage of females of *S. litura* was recorded (48.27±1.08; at 720 ppm) followed by (52.33±1.60; at 1440 ppm), (55.30±3.38; at 1680 ppm), (64.22±2.98; at 1200 ppm), (85.88±1.66; at 960 ppm) and control (93.07±5.01; at 00 ppm).

Table- 1. Larval mortality percentage of *S. litura* under laboratory conditions

Treatment	Dose	Concentration in ppm	Larval mortality (%) Mean ± SE
Methoxyfenozide 24 hours	1	1680	16.67±3.33
	2	1440	13.33±3.33
	3	1200	3.33±3.33
	4	960	3.33±3.33
	5	720	0.00±0.00
48 hours	1	1680	20.00±0.00
	2	1440	20.00±0.00
	3	1200	10.00±0.00
	4	960	6.67±3.33
	5	720	0.00±0.00
72 hours	1	1680	56.67±3.33
	2	1440	56.67±8.82
	3	1200	3.33±6.67
	4	960	23.33±3.33
	5	720	13.33±3.33
96 hours	1	1680	76.67±3.33
	2	1440	66.67±6.67
	3	1200	50.00±5.77
	4	960	23.33±3.33
	5	720	23.33±3.33
One week	1	1680	80.00±0.00
	2	1440	70.00±5.77
	3	1200	53.33±6.67
	4	960	30.00±5.77
	5	720	23.33±3.33
Control	Distilled water	00	0.00±0.00

Table-2. Larval weight reduction percentage of *S. litura* under laboratory conditions

Treatment	Dose	Concentration in ppm	Larval weight reduction (%) Mean ± SE
Methoxyfenozide 24 hours	1	1680	24.88±0.08
	2	1440	16.98±0.09
	3	1200	6.30±0.15
	4	960	8.60±0.09

	5	720	8.22±0.05
48 hours	1	1680	32.69±0.04
	2	1440	27.26±0.04
	3	1200	17.21±0.07
	4	960	19.26±0.12
	5	720	14.61±0.03
72 hours	1	1680	59.83±0.11
	2	1440	62.05±0.19
	3	1200	41.24±0.13
	4	960	36.29±0.18
	5	720	31.18±0.06
96 hours	1	1680	80.16±0.02
	2	1440	77.29±0.28
	3	1200	58.30±0.08
	4	960	44.78±0.12
	5	720	38.82±0.11
One week	1	1680	83.01±0.03
	2	1440	81.76±0.22
	3	1200	63.71±0.06
	4	960	52.31±0.07
	5	720	44.55±0.12
Control	Distilled water	00	0.00±0.00

Table-3. Larval, pupal period, pupal weight, development time, adult longevity and total life period of *S. litura* under laboratory conditions

Treatment	Dose	Concentration in ppm	Larval weight reduction (%) Mean ± SE
Methoxyfenozide larval period	1	1680	27.17±0.60
	2	1440	25.83±0.26
	3	1200	24.40±0.12
	4	960	23.63±0.26
	5	720	22.33±0.08
Control			14.23±0.09
Pupal period	1	1680	12.06±0.44
	2	1440	11.50±0.30
	3	1200	10.20±0.55
	4	960	9.16±0.24
	5	720	8.20±0.11
Control			6.80±0.15
Pupal weight	1	1680	42.23±0.63
	2	1440	40.33±0.49
	3	1200	37.60±0.75
	4	960	35.80±0.75

	5	720	33.53±0.18
Control			24.03±0.34
Development time	1	1680	42.23±0.63
	2	1440	40.33±0.49
	3	1200	37.60±0.75
	4	960	35.80±0.75
	5	720	33.53±0.18
			24.03±0.34
Adult longevity	1	1680	7.06±0.41
	2	1440	8.13±0.03
	3	1200	8.63±0.26
	4	960	9.83±0.52
	5	720	10.36±0.38
Control			11.83±0.44
Total life period	1	1680	49.36±0.21
	2	1440	48.33±0.34
	3	1200	46.23±0.90
	4	960	45.76±0.76
	5	720	44.06±0.31
Control	Distilled water	00	35.86±0.73

Table-4. Sex ratio (♂:♀) comparisons

Treatment	Dose (ppm)	Total pupae	Emerged	Not emerged	Male (average)	Female (average)	Sex ratio
Methoxifenozone	1680	6	5	1	1	4	1:4
	1440	9	8	1	3	5	3:5
	1200	14	12	2	3	9	1:3
	960	21	18	3	5	13	5:13
	720	23	21	1	7	14	1:2
Control	00	30	30	0	10	20	1:2

Table-5. Copulation time, Fecundity, Fertility of *S. litura* (F.) under laboratory conditions

Treatment	Dose	Concentration in ppm	Larval weight reduction (%) Mean ± SE
Methoxyfenozone copulation time	1	1680	30.16±0.33
	2	1440	27.83±0.16
	3	1200	25.16±0.33
	4	960	22.66±0.16
	5	720	20.66±0.33
Control			57.00±0.00
Fecundity	1	1680	341.67±7.54
	2	1440	365.33±4.67
	3	1200	402.00±3.51
	4	960	356.67±1.33
	5	720	483.00±4.04

Control			1178.00±50.52
Fertility	1	1680	55.30±3.38
	2	1440	52.33±1.60
	3	1200	64.22±2.98
	4	960	85.88±1.66
	5	720	48.27±1.08
Control	Distilled water	00	93.07±5.01

DISCUSSION

The present research studies on the productivity of methoxyfenozide on the biological parameters of *Spodoptera litura* (F.) were done under laboratory conditions at the Department of Entomology, Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam during, 2015-16. The larvae were gathered from vegetable fields of Tando Allahyar district: Hyderabad. Treated food was given to fourth instar larvae for two days (48 hours). *S. litura* is the broad-based insect species throughout the world wide. It has a number of common names including the tobacco caterpillar, tropical armyworm, armyworm, cluster caterpillar, cotton leafworm or tobacco cutworm. It belongs to Phylum: Arthropoda, Subphylum: Uniramia, Order: Lepidoptera, Family: Noctuidae and Subfamily: Amphipyrrinae. It is distributed widespread in Asia, Oceania, North America (USA: Hawaii only) (EPP0), Russia and UK [22]. It attacks on soybean in Kota region of Rajasthan and a loss of Rs: 300 crore was estimated [23]. Larvae are the most destructive pest, that vestige in the cultivated crop up to development and demonstrate utmost harm during the vegetative stage where sufficient chlorophyll is there [24]. Pest appearance was originated to be linked with food availability [25] and suitable climatic condition where it attacks not only leaves but tunnels in the stem of the plant [26]. This pest attacks on tomato, rice, corn, eggplant, potato, sweet and hot peppers, tobacco [27], cotton, okra, cabbage, cauliflower, radish, peanut and other legumes [28]. This is also known as cluster caterpillar, common cutworm, cotton leafworm, tobacco cutworm, tobacco caterpillar, and tropical armyworm. Tobacco caterpillar is usually a pest of cauliflower and cabbage [29] that breeds throughout the year that develops six larval stages feed up to 15-30 days. Further it depends on the potential climate change but losses up to 30% cotton leaves [10^b] and 90% defoliation of sunflower [30]. *S. litura* is recognized as a serious pest with substantial host range causing higher economic losses to crops at their blossoming and vegetative stages with 70 to 100% yield loss [31] attacks approximately 150 plants with its sporadic attack on cauliflower.

The mortality and sub-lethal effects of methoxyfenozide were determined on biology of surviving *S. litura*. The results indicated that the methoxyfenozide treatment caused mortality, reduction in larval and pupal weight and adult longevity, increased the duration of the life cycle. The copulation time, fecundity and fertility decreased as compared to control. The maximum mortality of *S. litura* was caused by methoxyfenozide on dose one after one week and minimum on dose five after 24 hours. The larval weight was also reduced by this insecticide the maximum larval weight reduction was recorded in dose one after one week and dose three after 24 hours. The longest larval and pupal period was recorded in dose one and shortest in dose five as compared to control. The maximum pupal weight reduction was recorded in dose one and minimum in dose five as compared to control. The shortest adult longevity of *S. litura* was recorded in dose one and highest in dose five as compared to control [32] revealed the bio-efficacy of 5 pesticides such as; indoxacarb, methomyl, fipronil, thiamethoxam

and imidacloprid against 7 day old larvae of *S. litura* by leaf dip method. Indoxacarb was the most toxic insecticide at 24 h exposure, at all the three concentrations. A trial was also conducted under laboratory conditions to assess the relative efficacy of some new chemicals such as; emamectin benzoate, indoxacarb, fipronil and methoxyfenoxide against *S. litura* of 3rd stage larvae under laboratory conditions [33]. The toxicity of different insecticides against *S. litura* was observed on emamectin benzoate (6.93), fenvalerate (1.82), indoxacarb (1.62), cypermethrin (1.00), abamectin (0.94), quinalphos (0.67), spinosad (0.44), endosulfan (0.28), betacyfluthrin (0.23), lambda cyhalothrin (0.19) [34]. The abamectin had minimum lethal concentration value of 271.416 ppm against *S. litura*, while novaluron had the maximum lethal concentration at 1976.430 ppm [35, 36] also evaluated the effectiveness of some synthetic pyrethroids against *S. litura* in Rajasthan. Lethal concentration value of 4 insecticides such as; emamectin benzoate, spinosad, imidacloprid and profenofos were evaluated against a population of *S. litura* under laboratory conditions. Emamectin benzoate (1.59 ppm) was found to be most toxic of lethal concentration values of spinosad (7.77 ppm), profenofos (686.5 ppm) and imidacloprid (258.75 ppm) [37].

The longest duration of life-cycle was recorded in dose one and shortest in dose five as compared to control. The shortest copulation time was recorded in dose one and highest in dose five as compared to control. Minimum fecundity was recorded in dose one and highest in dose five as compared to control, whereas the minimum fertility of eggs was recorded in dose one and highest in dose five as compared to control. From the results mentioned above it is concluded that the methoxyfenozide is insect growth regulators effective by their sub-lethal concentrations on *S. litura*. However, most preference can be given to which caused highly sub-lethal effects on biology. It was first recorded from New Zealand as a pest of tobacco and it has appeared in significant numbers in home garden and on crops [38]. The host range of this species covers over 40 families of economic importance crop species [39]. Among the main crop species attacked are cotton, soybean, groundnut, tobacco and vegetable crops such as cabbage and cauliflower in India, China, Pakistan and Bangladesh [40, 41]. The pest is known to cause 26-100% losses in groundnut [42], 38.51 in soybean and 70% in urdbean avoidable losses [43]. The pest is also known to cause 33.33-40.56, 77.86 and 90% foliage damage to potato, groundnut and sunflower [44, 32]. The extent of damage varies from 80-100% in tobacco nurseries and 10-15% in planted crops [45]. In heavy infestation it can seriously defoliate a crop. The outbreak of this insect generally occurs with a good rainfall after a long dry spell [46]. The tobacco caterpillar is known as a polyphagous insect having about 150 host species [47, 48]. These flourish under warm and humid field conditions of Asian countries causing higher economic losses to crops at their blossoming and vegetative stages with 70 to 100% yield loss [49]. In Punjab, this pest arises in sporadic form principally on cauliflower but is also observed feeding on other crops such as; C.

esculenta, *V. radiata*, *H. annuus*, *G. hirsutum* and *R. communis* [50]. Besides, such pesticides, organochlorines, organophosphates, carbamates and pyrethroids have also been recommended for *S. litura* [11]. The conventional pesticides under laboratory conditions, but chlorpyrifos, profenofos, emamectin benzoate, spinosad, indoxacarb, methoxyfenozide and lufenuron proved highly toxic [51]. Besides, the susceptibility of new insecticide on cotton and sub-lethal of neem oil concentration on cauliflower was also assessed against *S. litura* [52]. It is further concluded that the biological parameters of tobacco cutworm unambiguously prejudiced by the ability of methoxyfenozide under laboratory conditions.

CONCLUSION

Insect pests and insecticides have dangerously exaggerated the farm based occupation in rural areas of the major cauliflower cultivated fields at Tando Allahyar, Sindh. It was concluded from the research findings that the longest larval, pupal period, shortest adult longevity, maximum pupal weight reduction, longest duration of life-cycle, minimum copulation time, minimum fecundity, fertility of eggs and (♂:♀) ratio were recorded in dose one and highest in dose five. Therefore, it is further suggested that the methoxyfenozide (IGR) provided the best effective results by their sub-lethal concentrations so should be used under field cultivated crops against tobacco cutworm to diminish the pest population.

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